

A Study of Clinico-Epidemiological Profile of Lichen Planus and Its Association with Systemic Diseases in Patients Attending a Tertiary Care Centre, West Bengal

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Abstract:

Introduction: It is a common disorder, comprising more than 0.5% of all dermatological visits. It may be familial in 1–2% of cases. The aim of this study is to find out the incidence of lichen planus in different age and sex groups, seasonal variation, occupation and familial association. And to correlate any association of lichen planus with systemic diseases.

Methodology: An institution based cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in Dermatology (OPD) of Bankura Sammilani Medical College & Hospital, Bankura in Eastern India from March 2015 to February 2016. The study included 125 patients with typical feature of lichen planus of skin, nail, hair and mucous membrane.

Results: In our study 79/145 (54.5%) were females and 66/145 (45.5%) were males with sex ratio of 0.8:1 (male: female). Most common age group was 20–40 years and type were classical lichen planus (64.8%) followed by oral LP (16.8%) cases, linear LP (1.6%) cases, actinic LP (2.4%) cases, lichen planus pigmentosus, annular & genital lichen planus was seen in 2.4%. Koebner's phenomenon was seen in 50.4% cases. 0.8% case had involvement of scalp hair, with scarring alopecia, diabetes mellitus was seen in 6.4% cases, 5.6% of cases to have hypothyroidism, the frequency of HCV in association with lichen planus was 9.6%. Out of total 5 vitiligo patients 4 (80%, n=5) were below 20 yrs of age and 1 (20%, n=5) patient in >60-year age group. Out of total 12 Hepatitis C patients 5 (41.6% n=12) were in 21 years to 40-year age group and out of total 125 patients 52 (41.6% n=125) patients are in 21 years to 40-year age group. In present study we didn't find any case of palmoplantar LP, LP pemphigoides and zosteriform lichen planus that has been reported in other studies although LP pemphigoides is now consider as a variant of BP.

Conclusion: Lichen planus, an autoimmune disorder has a frequent association with other autoimmune diseases. HCV, diabetes mellitus and alopecia areata are the most common entities while, vitiligo, chronic active hepatitis, myasthenia gravis and thyroid disorders are seen less frequently.

Keywords: Systemic diseases, autoimmune, lichen planus.

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Introduction

Lichen planus (LP) is a unique, common chronic inflammatory and immune mediated disease that affects the skin, nails, hair, and mucous membranes [1]. Cutaneous lichen planus (CLP) most commonly involves the flexor surfaces of the extremities and presents as small itchy violaceous

Papules in middle aged adults. "Pruritic, Purple, Polygonal, Planar, Papules, and Plaques" are the traditional 6 "P's" of LP [2]. The pattern of LP detected and the age distribution vary among various genetic and geographic groups. In persons of European descent, it appears largely after the age of

20, and peaks between 40 and 70 years. Very few cases appear after age 80. Childhood LP typically accounts for 5% or less of cases.

However, in some regions, childhood cases are responsible for more than 10% of all LP cases. These areas include the Indian subcontinent, Arab countries, and Mexico. Race appears to be the critical factor, since in the UK 80% of childhood LP is seen in Indians. LP has been reported in association with diseases of altered or disturbed immunity [diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism, vitiligo, alopecia areata, SLE, thymoma, myasthenia

gravis etc [3]. Different studies were conducted in western countries. Our study is conducted in present population of eastern India.

Aims and Objectives

To find out the magnitude of the disease burden of LP among patient attending OPD of a tertiary care centre and determined the different clinical patterns of LP and the frequency of systemic diseases including autoimmune disorders associated with lichen planus and to compare our results with literature.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Dermatology (OPD) of Bankura Sammilani Medical College & Hospital, Bankura in Eastern India from March 2015 to February 2016 in all patients of LP attending Dermatology OPD. The study was an institution based cross-sectional descriptive study. The study included 125 patients with typical feature of lichen planus of skin, nail, hair and mucous membrane.

Inclusion Criteria: Clinically diagnosed new LP cases.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients were not willing to participate in the study
2. Those receiving treatment a priori

Institutional Ethics Committee approval was taken before initiation of the research project. Individual written informed consent was taken from all participants. Clinical features like age, sex, number, type of lichen planus, location was recorded in the case record form from the Dermatology OPD. All morphological features were also noted for comparison with clinical subtype. Fisher’s exact test was used to assess associations between various variables. All analyses were performed using SPSS software. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Chart 1: Roadmap of the Study

Results

LP is a disease with worldwide distribution in general population with prevalence of <1% [4]. A study of clinical histopathological and aetiological pattern of LP in 375 patient was done in part of Western Rajasthan [5].

The incidence of LP was 0.8%. There was male preponderance (58% of cases) and majority (46.93%) were in age group 20-39 years. Out of total

125 patients 35 (28% n=125) are above poverty line and 90 (72%, n=125) are below poverty line. BPL socio-economic status people were highly affected from LP.

$$\text{Prevalence} = (\text{no. of old} + \text{new cases} / \text{total population size}) \times 1000$$

$$= (798/86270) \times 1000 = 9.2/1000 \text{ population}$$

Figure 1: Diagram showing categorization of study population according to race and sex

Out of total 125 LP patients enrolled in the study 69 (55.2%, n=125) were males and 56 (44.8%, n=125) were females. About 37 (29.6%, n=125) non- tribals and 88 (70.4%, n=125) were tribals (Fig 1).

Sex Ratio: 1.2:1[M:F]

Figure 2: Diagram showing categorization of study population according to sex.

Sex ratio in the above study is 1:2 (M:F) [Fig. 2].

Figure 3: Diagram showing distribution of patients according to age group

Out of total 125 patients 21(16.8%) patients were <20 yrs of age, in 20-to-40-year age group 52 (41.6%) pts. 40 (32%) & 12 (9.6%) patients were respectively in 40 to 60 & >60-year age group. Mean age of patients was 38.5 ± 17.5 years [Fig. 3].

Table 1: Showing age distribution among different types of LP

Type	Age (Years)				Total	P value
	<20	21-40	41-60	>60		
Eruptive	18	33	25	5	81	
Oral	1	10	7	3	21	
LPH	0	3	3	0	6	
Linear	1	1	0	0	2	
Follicular+Nonfollicular	0	1	0	0	1	
Actinic+Genital	0	0	0	2	2	0.01
Multiple Annular	0	0	1	0	1	
Eruptive+ Oral	1	1	2	0	4	
Genital	0	0	0	1	1	
LPP	0	0	1	0	1	
Eruptive+ Oral+LPH	0	0	1	0	1	
Eruptive+Linear	0	2	0	0	2	
Oral+ Actinic+Genital	0	1	0	0	1	
Oral+Genital	0	0	0	1	1	
Total	21	52	40	12	125	

Figure 4: Diagram showing age distribution among different types of LP

Out of total 81eruptive LP patients 33/81(40.7%) patients were fall in 21-40 years age group which is highest in Eruptive LP patients. Out of total 125 LP patients 52(41.6%) patients were fall in 21-40 years age group with all LP type

patients which is highest in all age group. In <20 years age group patients were highly affected with Eruptive LP then followed by oral LP, Linear LP, and Eruptive+Oral LP with 1 patient in each [Table 1/ Fig. 4].

Table 2: Showing type distribution of LP patients associated to systemic diseases and other autoimmune diseases

Type	Associated with Systemic Diseases and other autoimmune diseases									Total	P value
	Nil	DM	MG	AA	Hypo-thy-roid-	Hypo-thy-roid-ism +DM	Viti-ligo	Hepa-titis C			
Eruptive	58	4	1	3	2	0	4	9	81		
Oral	13	2	0	0	3	1	1	1	21		
LPH	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	6		
Linear	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2		
Follicular+Nonfollicular	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
Actinic+Genital	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2		
Multiple Annular	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.57	
Eruptive+ Oral	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	4		
Genital	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1		
LPP	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
Eruptive+ Oral+LPH	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
Eruptive+Linear	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2		
Oral+ Actinic+Genital	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1		
Oral+Genital	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
Total	87	8	1	5	6	1	5	12	125		

Out of total 125 LP patients 50 (40% n=125) were males and 37 (29.6% n=125) were females which were not associated with any systemic diseases and other autoimmune diseases. Out of total 6 Hypothyroidism LP patients 1 (16.6%) was male and 5 (83.3%) were females and out of total 125 LP patient 1 (0.8%) females was associated with hypothyroidism plus type 2 DM. Female patients are highly affected than males in hypothyroidism and hypothyroidism plus type2 DM. Out of total 125 LP patients 12 (9.6%) patients had Hepatitis C in which 5 were males and 7 were females [Table 2]. Out of total 81 eruptive LP patients, 8 (9.8%, n=81) patients were affected with nail and 73 (90.1%, n=81) patients were not affected with nail. Out of total 21 oral LP patients, 1(4.7%, n=21) patient was affected with nail and 20 (95.2%, n=21) patients were not affected with nail and out of total 125 LP patients, 10 (8%, n=125) patients were affected with nail. Out of total 21 oral LP patients 1(4.7%, n=21) patients were affected with scarring alopecia and 20 (95.2%, n=21) patients were not affected with scarring alopecia. Out of total 125 LP patients 1(0.8%, n=125) patients was affected with scarring alopecia and 124 (99.2%, n=125) patients were not affected with scarring alopecia. Out of total 125 LP patients 115 (92%, n=125) patients are not having any family history in LP and 10 (8%, n=125) patients are having family history in LP. Out of total 81 eruptive LP patients 8 (9.8%, n=81) patients were having family history and 73 (90.1%, n=81) patients were not having family history. Out of total 125 LP patients only 3(2.4%, n=125) eruptive LP patients who they were not in any occupation. Out of total 125 LP patients 48(38.4%, n=125) LP patients were Farmer and 45(36%, n=125) LP patients were housewives and 22 (17.6%, n=125) LP patients were students by

occupation. Farmers and housewives are highly affected from all type of LP than other occupation. Out of total 125 LP patients 22(17.6%, n=125) LP patients had koebnerization over extremities, 33(26.4%, n=125) LP patients had koebnerization over trunk and extremities which is highly significant (p value <0.01)

Discussion

The study was conducted in the Department of Dermatology OPD of Bankura Sammilani Medical College & Hospital, Bankura in Eastern India. Total 86,270 patients were attended in our OPD from March 2015 to February 2016, out of which total LP cases were 798. So prevalence in our study were 0.92%. After a detailed history, complete general, cutaneous and systemic examination was carried out. In addition to routine investigations, any relevant investigations when required were also carried out. All the findings were recorded, compiled, tabulated and analyzed. Retrospectively we analyzed all the cases of lichen planus received in our department in 1 year's study duration from March 2015 to February 2016. A total of 125 new clinically diagnosed lichen planus samples were included for studying the clinicoepidemiological aspects of lichen planus and its association with systemic diseases.

In our study 79/145 (54.5%) were females and 66/145 (45.5%) were males with sex ratio of 0.8:1 (Male: Female). Majority of the patients of lichen planus were in the age group of 20–40 years. The age range of the patients was from 3 years to 92 years in males and 3 years to 72 years in females. Some patients sought help as early as a few days after its onset, while others, had the disease for

several years. All the cases (125) are divided into different subgroups based on clinical variants as well as on the basis of anatomic distribution as involving head and neck, trunk, upper limb, lower limb or others (nail or mucosal involvement). Lesions of lichen planus (classical type) were mostly present on lower extremities while those of lichen planus pigmentosus and lichen planopilaris had head and neck as their predominant site of involvement.

A significant association was found between the age of the patient and the occurrence of classical lichen

planus on lower limb (p value= 0.016). It was observed that involvement of lower limb was more common in younger age group as 52/125 patients (41.6%) in the age group between 20-40 years and 21/125 patients (16.8%) in the age group of less than 20 years had lower limb involvement. This association gradually decreased as the age increased. A significant association was also seen between female gender and involvement of upper limb by lichen planus (p value = 0.031).

Table 3: Comparison of clinical type of lichen planus in various studies

Type of Lichen Planus	Present Study	O P Singh et al[6]	Kacchaw a Dilip et al[7]	Salah A Abdallat et al[8]	Garg Vijay Kumar et al[9]	Vijayasin gam et al [10]	Tag -EL - Din Anbar et al [11]
Classical LP	64.8%	74.61%	52%	57.5%	73.3%	64%	30%
LPH	4.8%	12.70%	1.87%	17.8%	17.3%	11%	12%
Linear LP	1.6%	-	2.4%	-	-	-	-
Actinic lp	2.4%	-	14.13%	-	4%	-	36%
LP Pigmentosus	0.8%	-	6.52%	-	-	-	-
Annular LP	0.8%	-	0.27%	-	-	-	-
Lichen Plano Piliaris	0.8%	1.81%	2.67%	1.2%	2.7%	-	4%
Oral LP	16.8%	4.76%	-	13.77%	2.7%	17%	8%

Classical lichen planus was the commonest type in all the studies except Tag-El-Din Anbar et al, [11] Who found actinic type of lichen planus was most common type. Classical lichen planus was the most common type found in our study with 20 to 40 years being common age group. A similar dominance of classical lichen planus over other variants has been reported in the literature by various authors in addition to above studies (Bhattacharya et al., 2000) [12].

In our series, maximum numbers of patients were seen in the age group of 20–40 years. This correlates with other studies that describes data of Indian population (Bhattacharya et al., 2000;

Singh and Kanwar, 1976) [12, 6] however in the western literature (Andreason, 1968)[13] an older age is reported. Difference in the age range between male and female was about a decade, which corresponds with western literature (Andreason, 1968)[13]. Furthermore, in the Western literature LP is considered to be rare in children (Mellgren and Hersle, 1965)[14] However, it is not uncommon in the Indian subcontinent (Kanwar and De, 2010)[15]. In our study we found that 21(16.8%) out of 125 patients were less than 20 years of age. Out of these 21 patients only 2 patients had positive family history. This increased incidence of childhood LP in the Indian population as compared to western literature may be due to lack of data from other populations or due to some unidentifiable environmental factors (Black, 1992) [16]. Although we found that children are more commonly affected with lichen planus in Indian population than western

countries, there was statistically significant (p value 0.01) correlation between any age group and occurrence of different types of lichen planus in Indian population, as we found that disease was more common in 20 to 40 years age group in Indian population.

In our study we found that male gender is more commonly affected with lichen planus than females. In the literature there has been no consistency regarding any sex preference of LP (White, 1919; Altman and Perry, 1961)[17, 19] but most of the studies have shown that females are more commonly affected than males (Little, 1919; White, 1919; Altman and Perry, 1961)[17-19]. In our series, we found that lower limbs (61.6%) were the most common site to be affected in classical lichen planus which is similar to the observation that has been reported in various studies and venous stasis has been offered as a likely explanation [12,13,20] No definite cause could be ascertained regarding the localization of lesions to lower limbs in our study. However, one interesting thing that we found is a statistically significant association of involvement of lower limb in a younger age group (<20years). Head and neck were the most common site of involvement in lichen planus pigmentosus and lichen planopilaris.

A statistically significant association was also seen between female gender and upper limb involvement. No such associations have been described in the literature till date to the best of our knowledge. The lesions in these cases were generalized in distribution with lesions predominantly on

extremities. Oral lichen planus was the second common type found in 16.8% cases, cases of hypertrophic lichen planus had longer duration of disease. Similar finding has been reported by Vijayasin Gam et al [10], hypertrophic lichen planus was the next most common form found in 4.8%% cases. Actinic lichen planus was seen in 2.4%% cases, the lesions in this type were predominantly distributed on sun-exposed areas like forearms, face & V-neck. Some of these patients complained of burning sensation. Similar findings were found by O P Singh et al [6] in its study. Lichen planus pigmentosus was seen in single female patient. In this case lesions were predominantly seen on upper trunk & face. Upper and lower extremities were less frequently involved. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies (Kanwar et al., 2003) [15]. Associated nail and mucosal involvement was infrequent in LPP. This is in concordance with other studies (Kanwar et al., 2003) [15]. Palmoplantar LP was not seen in our study. In present study we didn't find any case of palmoplantar LP, LP pemphigoides and zosteriform lichen planus that has been reported in other studies although LP pemphigoides is now consider as a variant of BP.

In present study Koebner's phenomenon was seen in 50.4% cases. It is statistically significant (p value <0.01). Most of the cases that had Koebner's phenomenon complained of itching that was quite severe. Sanjeev Handa et al [21] in study of childhood lichen planus found Koebner's phenomenon in 26.5% cases. In our study, 75.2% cases had lesions only on skin, 8% cases had lesions on skin & mucous membranes & 16.8% had lesions only on mucous membranes. Our findings correlate with the figures found in studies mentioned in above table 3. Our study findings of skin involvement correlated with other studies. But, lower incidence of mucosal membrane in our study may be because cases of oral lichen planus are seen by dentists. The low incidence of mucous membrane involvement may also be explained by the fact that in this institution, Department of Dermatology refers patients to the Department of E.N.T. for obtaining oral mucosal biopsies, and to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology for obtaining genital mucosal biopsies. This may lead to unavoidable loss of data. In our study oral mucosa involvement was seen in 16.8% cases with reticular involvement of buccal mucosa being the most common presentation. O P Singh et al [6] & Tag-El-Din Anbar et al [11] found oral involvement in 27.21% & 22% cases with reticulate pattern being the common presentation. Oral involvement in lichen planus is seen frequently and reticular form is the common type of lesion.

In our study, nail involvement was seen in 8% of cases. Longitudinal ridging was the commonest finding seen in 4.34% cases. Our findings correlate

with Salah A Abdallat et al [8] who found nail involvement in 9% cases with longitudinal ridging being the commonest finding. Garg Vijay Kumar et al [9] found nail involvement in 9.33% cases. Kacchawa Dilip et al [7] found nail involvement in 6.4% cases while O P Singh et al found it only in 1.6% cases, V N Sehgal & Rege et al [22] didn't find any nail involvement in their study. Bhattacharya et al found it in 15.1% cases. Vijayasingam et al [9] found nail involvement in 3% cases. Tag-El-Din Anbar et al [11] found it in 18% cases. One of our cases had twenty nail dystrophy. Nail biopsy was not done for this patient. There have been several reports of twenty nail dystrophy associated with lichen planus [22].

In our study we found that 1 (0.8%) case had involvement of scalp hair, with scarring alopecia. Our findings correlate with Salah A Abdallat et al [8] who found hair involvement in 1.2% cases. Tag-El-Din Anbar et al [11] found cicatricial alopecia in 4% of these cases. In our study, diabetes mellitus was seen in 6.4% cases. In most of the patient's diabetes mellitus had an onset after the onset of lichen planus. Seyhan M et al [23] found 26.7% cases of lichen planus were diabetics. Nigam et al [24] found abnormalities of oral glucose tolerance test of the nature of type II diabetes mellitus in 30.3% cases of lichen planus. Y. Gül Denli et al [20] found diabetes in 15.7% cases of lichen planus. The association has not been proven conclusively. There is need for further study to establish the validity of this association. In our study, we found hypertension in 4.34% cases. Kacchawa Dilip et al [7] found hypertension among 2.4% of cases. We also found 5.6% of cases to have hypothyroidism. Multiple autoimmune disorders occur with increased frequency in patients with a previous history of another autoimmune disease [25] Some disorders are associated with LP more frequently than is expected by chance.

In our study, the frequency of HCV in association with lichen planus was 9.6%. There have been reports worldwide regarding this association with variable frequencies. Prabhu et al [26] reported that none of their 65 patients was HCV positive. However, there are wide geographical variations in the reported prevalence of HCV infection in patients with lichen planus. So far, many case-controlled studies have been undertaken implicating or refuting the association of HCV with LP.

Most of the positive studies are from Japan, Spain and Italy [27-30]. The studies from Northern UK have persistently failed to establish an association between hepatitis C infection and lichen planus [31,32]. Despite this contradiction, the finding in our study is in agreement with other studies in our part of the world [33]. Diabetes mellitus has been reported to be associated with lichen planus in literature [34]. The frequency of diabetes mellitus in

our study in association with lichen planus was 6.4%. All the patients with diabetes mellitus also had oral lesions. Being a common skin disorders, lichen planus and alopecia areata may rarely coexist. 5 patients with lichen planus in our study had alopecia areata concomitantly (4 %). Kar [35] and Madris et al [36] have also reported this association. In the current study the coexistence of vitiligo and LP is also described with or without the presence of other autoimmune diseases [37-38]. The association of LP with liver disease is now well-established. Recent reports suggest that hepatitis viruses may play a central role in this association. An association between autoimmune thyroid disorders and lichen planus has been reported in literature. Despite all these reports and the current study, large scale studies are further required to determine the frequency of autoimmune diseases associated with lichen planus.

There have been several systemic diseases described in association with lichen planus. There is need for further study to understand the association and its importance in etiopathogenesis of lichen planus.

Conclusion

LP is a T cell mediated disease. The prevalence of LP is less than 5% with no evident sexual predilection. Classical lichen planus is the most common clinical variant of lichen planus, followed by oral lichen planus and hypertrophic lichen planus. Hypertrophic lichen planus was associated with longer duration of disease and severe pruritus.

HCV (9.6%) and DM (6.4%) are more prevalent in LP patients compared to the normal population. Lichen planus is a disease of adults (20–40 years) according to western data but in Indian population it is also common in the paediatric age group (<18 years). The disease is relatively more common in females than males. Classical lichen planus has a strong association of involvement of the extremities in the younger age group. Involvement of upper limb is more common in female patients in lichen planus. Lichen planus, an autoimmune disorder has a frequent association with other autoimmune diseases. HCV, diabetes mellitus and alopecia areata are the most common entities while, vitiligo, chronic active hepatitis, myasthenia gravis and thyroid disorders are seen less frequently. Therefore, the presence of lichen planus should alert the physician to watch for other autoimmune disorders.

Limitations

DIF is sometimes helpful in diagnosis of certain variants of lichen planus which mimics to other cutaneous diseases but due to institutional unavailability proper diagnosis of these cases could not be achieved. The study period is also only one year and single centre. So, a larger study with multiple study centers done on a longer period will

be able to define the situation more accurately and more statistical power could be achieved.

Ethics Approval: From Institutional Ethics Committee, Bankura Sammilani Medical College & Hospital, Bankura, West Bengal

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